

Ad-hoc statement

Sars-CoV-2: the pandemic is definitely not over yet

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Abstract

The latest figures from the United Kingdom and Israel show that the delta variant (Indian mutation) can spread despite a high rate of vaccination. It can be assumed that the vaccines continue to provide fairly reliable protection against severe disease. But there is still a lack of sufficiently robust data on this, too. The Covid-19 pandemic is by no means over.

Situation report

Those who thought that high vaccination rates alone could defeat the covid pandemic are currently being proven wrong. Of course, the vaccines and the high vaccination rates are important, but without supporting measures, the pandemic will never end. However, the number of severe illnesses and deaths remains at a comparatively low level. Still, despite an emerging wave of disease, the United Kingdom still plans to lift all control measures on July 19. In Israel¹, vaccination of young people is being pushed. In the United Kingdom, 27,334 new confirmed COVID-19 cases were reported Monday. The 7-day incidence has now risen to more than 220 per 100,000 population.² The increase in case numbers that began in mid-May has continued, despite 86% of the population had the 1st vaccine dose and 64% the 2nd vaccine dose. According to Public Health England, the delta variant now accounts for 95% of infections.³ The UK government plans to relax measures despite the sharp increase in the number of cases. The requirement to wear masks has already been lifted, and all restrictions are due to fall on July 19, "Freedom Day."

The British government obviously hopes that the delta variant will only cause mild illness - although the data on this is so far scarce and contradictory. The British are counting on the high rate of complete vaccinations in the older age groups to prevent the worst. In the over-50s, the rate is over 80%, and in the over-70s it is even over 90%. By contrast, of those under 40, only 12% received both doses so far.² Some scientists, meanwhile, place their hopes on the possibility that young people may be protected by earlier infections that they may not have noticed. However, this opinion is as unproven as it is controversial. So far, the government's hopes have been realized, but the data won't become truly robust until late July to early August. An increase in mortality, which was greater during the 2nd wave than in other European countries, is not yet apparent. The number of hospitalizations has started to increase despite Public Health England interprets the rise as a not very significant change.⁹ Numerous colleagues in the field of virology caution, however, that looking at severe illness alone may be shortsighted. Richard Tedder of Imperial College London worries that spread of the delta variant in the presence of partial immunity could encourage the emergence of more dangerous variants. He believes this to be inevitable if vaccinations only prevent severe disease but no longer prevent the infections themselves.⁸

In Israel⁹, the number of infections has also increased in recent days. The 7-day incidence is currently 22 confirmed cases per 100,000 inhabitants. Severe illnesses are still rare. There have been no deaths related to the virus in the past two weeks. However, there appears to be evidence of reduced protective efficacy of the vaccine, which in Israel is entirely the Pfizer-Biontech mRNA product.⁶ The Health Ministry in Jerusalem announced that the protective efficacy had dropped to 64% as the delta variant continued to spread throughout the country yesterday. In March, when infection was still dominated by the alpha variant, protection was 91%. At that time, most severe illnesses were prevented. This protective effect is currently still relatively

strong at 93%. The government is trying to get a grip on the situation by offering vaccinations to young people. In early July, all adolescents aged 12 and older were asked to get vaccinated. It is to be expected that the immune protection will weaken somewhat over time, but here, too, scientific consensus is still lacking.⁵ In Israel, vaccinations were administered very early. That protection against passing on the virus in particular could diminish over time has long been feared - it is considered less durable than the protection of the vaccinated person himself. In principle, it can be assumed that the delta variant could lead to more frequent breakthrough infections - i.e. infections in vaccinated persons - and also to the virus being passed on by vaccinated persons.⁷ However, it can be assumed that the vaccines continue to provide fairly reliable protection against severe disease. But there is still a lack of sufficiently robust data on this, too.

The covid pandemic is by no means over.

Conflicts of interest

None.

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